

Studies on Complex Formation of Zinc-, Copper-, Nickel-, Cobalt- and Manganese(II) with D(+)-Saccharic Acid

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The present communication describes the study of determination of stability constants of the neutral complex of some transition metal ions with D(+)-saccharic acid at low pH and the dissociation constant of its dissociation to other form of complexes at higher pH.

Results and Discussion

In the case of Ni^{II}-, Co^{II}-, Mn^{II}- and Zn^{II}-D(+)-saccharic acid systems, the liberation of proton during complex formation remained same when the metal-ligand ratio was increased from 1 : 1.25 to 1 : 5. This indicated the formation of only 1 : 1 type of complex. In the case of Cu^{II}-D(+)-saccharic acid system, both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 types of complex formation were indicated.

The reaction between the metal ion and D(+)-saccharic acid (H₂Sa) can be represented as

where C represents the 1 : 1 complex and *n* the number of proton liberated per g-atom of the metal ion. The values of *n* were calculated according to the method followed in earlier investigations¹. The values of *n* were found to be > 2 above pH 4.2, 5.4, 6.0, 6.0 and 5.6 for the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} systems respectively. Assuming the value of *n* to be 2 below these pH values in each system, the C and then the values of equilibrium constants (-log *K*₁^{*}) for the reaction (1) were calculated¹ (Table 1).

In the pH range 4.2-5.4 in the case of Cu^{II} system and above pH 5.4, 6.0, 6.0 and 5.6 in the case of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} systems respectively, the values of *n* were > 2 but < 3. Hence the complex (C) dissociates as

The liberation of this third proton is probably due to the coordination of one of the α-hydroxylic groups of the ligand with the metal ion. That one of the hydroxylic groups of the D(+)-saccharic acid was involved in bond formation with metal ions was established by the appearance of an ir band for the Cu^{II}- and Ni^{II}-D(+)-saccharate complexes^{2,3} at 2 600 cm⁻¹. The values of the equilibrium constant (-log *K*₂^{*}) for the reaction (2), were calculated as before (Table 1). Above pH 5.4 in the case of Cu^{II} system, the values of *n* were > 3 but < 4. This indicated the dissociation of the complex C⁻ to C²⁻ and a proton as

The liberation of this proton may be due to the coordination of a hydroxylic group of the sugar acid with the Cu^{II} ion. However, the possibility of the liberation of this proton from a coordinated water molecule cannot be ruled out. The values of the equilibrium constant (-log *K*₃) for the reaction (3) were determined⁴ (Table 1). In the case of 1 : 2 Cu^{II}-D(+)-saccharic acid system, the values of equilibrium constant (-log *K*_{1,2}^{*}) for the reaction, Cu²⁺ + 2H₂Sa ⇌ C_{1,2} + nH⁺, were calculated as before⁵ (Table 1).

In experiment-2 the reactions taking place can be represented as

The values of $\bar{n}A$, \bar{n} and *pL* were obtained by standard expressions⁶. The formation curves corresponding to the proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibrium were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}A$ and \bar{n} against pH and *pL* respectively. The

TABLE 1-PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Ligand : D(+)-saccharic acid, temp. = 25 ± 1°, I = 0.1 M (NaClO₄), p*K*₂^H = 3.13, p*K*₁^H = 4.2

Cation	Experiment-1				Experiment-2	
	-log <i>K</i> ₁ [*]	-log <i>K</i> ₂ [*]	-log <i>K</i> ₃ [*]	-log <i>K</i> _{1,2} [*]	log <i>K</i> ₁	log <i>K</i> ₂
Cu ^{II}	3.86	4.38	6.65	9.20	3.51	5.54
Ni ^{II}	4.02	7.33			3.35	
Co ^{II}	4.08	7.38			3.29	
Mn ^{II}	4.17	7.13			3.20	
Zn ^{II}	3.90	7.38			3.47	

$$\log K_1 = \log K_1^*/K_1^H \quad K_2^H \quad \log K_2 = \log K_{1,2}^*/(K_1^H K_2^H)^2$$

NOTE

values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H of the D(+)-saccharic acid obtained by various computational methods (Table 1) agreed well with the reported values^{2,7}. The values of stability constants, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were similarly obtained by different computational methods (Table 1). The relation between the equilibrium constants (K_1^* and $K_{1,2}^*$) and stability constants (K_1 and K_2) is also shown in Table 1. The $\log K_1$ values obtained in this experiment agreed well with that obtained in experiment-1. The $\log K_2$ value for the Cu^{II} system, however, did not agree with the respective value in experiment-1. This may be ascribed to the extensive formation of polynuclear complexes in Cu^{II} -D(+)-saccharic acid system. The linear nature of the plot of \bar{n}/L vs L (figure not shown) in the Cu^{II} system also supports this view. The order of stability, $Zn < Cu > Ni > Co > Mn$, obeys Irving William's rule⁷.

Experimental

All chemical used were of A.R. grade. D(+)-Saccharic acid was derived from insoluble D(+)-calcium saccharate by ionic exchange method⁹. pH-titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere with an Ecil-5652 pH meter at $25 \pm$

1° and 0.1 M ionic strength ($NaClO_4$) using CO_2 -free NaOH solution. The carbonate content of NaOH solution was assessed¹⁰. The pH-titrations were performed in duplicate to test reproducibility.

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